

GreenDIGIT

Greener Future Digital Research Infrastructures

Deliverable 5.3: Design and Operation of a Federated Data Management Infrastructure for Open Science Workflows

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p16-17 (sec. 2.5)	Added new section explaining “Automatic publishing on Zenodo” and how federation will work among RIs.
p9 (Figure 2)	Added new figure detailing FDMI Architectural.
p13 (Figure 5)	Updated the FDMI catalogue interface figure, which now includes option of “Browsing of RIs through Group”.
p14 (Figure 6)	Updated the experiment published in the FDMI figure, which now includes DOI metadata.
p16 (Figure 8)	New Figure added which shows publishing of a research product from the FDMI to Zenodo via web user interface.

p17 (Figure 9)

New Figure added which show the actual deposited Research Product in Zenodo.

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Executive Summary

This short report accompanies the deliverable “Design and Operation of a Federated Data Management Infrastructure for Open Science Workflows”, classified as a “DEM” (Demonstrator). It provides a concise overview of the design and deployment of the key software components constituting the Federated Data Management Infrastructure (FDMI), developed to meet the current operational needs of the GreenDIGIT community in support of open science workflows.

The FDMI demonstrator provides a metadata-driven catalogue that supports the publication, discovery, and reuse of research assets such as datasets and experiments, promoting FAIR and reproducible science practices. Research artefacts may be hosted within the D4Science infrastructure or referenced from external repositories such as Zenodo. The current implementation represents a prototype deployment, where the software components required for the FDMI are deployed and operated within the D4Science infrastructure.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
FDMI	Federated Data Management Infrastructure
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IdP	Identity Provider
JWT	JSON Web Token
OIDC	OpenID Connect
SSO	Single Sign-On
UMA 2	User-Managed Access 2.0

1 Introduction and overview

The **Federated Data Management Infrastructure (FDMI)** is a flexible and extensible system designed to support the data management needs of the project. The FDMI demonstrator represents a prototype implementation of a federated data management environment, aimed at enabling the **publication, discovery, and reuse** of heterogeneous research outputs, such as **experiments, datasets, and scientific workflows**, produced within the project. The infrastructure supports a wide and evolving range of community-defined data asset types, including experiments, datasets, and scientific workflows.

In the context of this demonstrator, the FDMI provides a metadata-driven catalogue and integration layer that enables users to describe, register, and discover research assets through rich metadata and standards-compliant interfaces. These capabilities facilitate FAIR data practices and support reproducibility by enabling transparent access to research artefacts and their associated metadata.

While the FDMI follows a federated architectural model, the current demonstrator should be understood as a prototype deployment operated within the D4Science infrastructure environment. In particular, D4Science provides, deploys, and operates the software components required for the functioning of the FDMI services used by the project. The federation aspect of the infrastructure is therefore realised through the integration of heterogeneous data sources and services through interoperable interfaces, rather than through independently operated infrastructure nodes.

Figure 1. FDMI reference architecture.

Figure 1 illustrates the FDMI’s reference architecture, composed of four main components:

- **(a) Web User Interface** – an intuitive environment for browsing, searching, and interacting with catalogue contents;
- **(b) RESTful API** – provides programmatic access for querying and publishing metadata;

- **(c) FDMI Service** – handles metadata storage, indexing, and coordination across infrastructure components;
- **(d) Metadata Profiles** – define the structure, semantics, and validation rules for each resource type.

The actual content referenced in the catalogue may be stored via **persistent URLs** or directly within the SoBigData e-infrastructure, ensuring interoperability and long-term support for reproducible research.

2 FDMI Architecture, Access Mechanisms, and User Interfaces

2.1 FDMI Architecture

The Federated Data Management Infrastructure (FDMI) is implemented as a modular and extensible system deployed within the D4Science infrastructure environment, which provides the computational and service platform supporting the operation of the demonstrator. In this context, D4Science is responsible for deploying, hosting, and operating the software components necessary for the functioning of the FDMI services used within the GreenDIGIT project. The current implementation should therefore be regarded as a prototype deployment of a federated data management solution.

The architecture of the FDMI demonstrator, illustrated in Figure 2, follows a service-oriented design that separates the user interaction layer, the catalogue services responsible for metadata management, and the underlying storage and indexing mechanisms.

Figure 2. FDMI architecture in detail within the D4Science Infrastructure

At the top layer, the FDMI Front-end provides the web-based user interface through which users can browse, search, and interact with the catalogue. The front-end is implemented using the open-source CKAN platform, which offers a mature framework for managing and publishing research metadata. Through this interface, users can explore datasets, experiments, and other research assets registered within the catalogue.

The front-end communicates with the FDMI Service (gCat), which represents the core service component of the infrastructure. The FDMI Service is responsible for managing catalogue operations,

including metadata ingestion, validation according to defined metadata profiles, indexing, and coordination with external services. It acts as the central middleware layer that connects the user interface to the underlying storage and indexing subsystems.

The metadata managed by the FDMI Service is stored and indexed using two complementary backend components:

- PostgreSQL Database, which provides persistent storage for catalogue metadata and system information;
- Apache Solr, which supports efficient indexing and search capabilities, enabling fast discovery and filtering of catalogue records through the user interface and APIs.

Together, these components ensure reliable storage and high-performance retrieval of metadata records. The architecture also integrates with other services available within the D4Science ecosystem, enabling interoperability with complementary infrastructure components. As shown on the left side of Figure 2, these services include capabilities such as:

- File Sync & Share services, supporting storage and sharing of research artefacts;
- URI Resolver service, enabling persistent identification and referencing of digital resources;
- Information Systems, providing integration with broader infrastructure-level services.

Through these integrations, FDMI can reference and manage research assets that may reside in distributed environments rather than being stored directly within the catalogue itself.

Finally, the infrastructure supports interoperability with external repositories, such as Zenodo (c.f. Sec 2.5), which can be used for long-term preservation and publication of datasets and research outputs. In this context, FDMI acts as a metadata catalogue and integration layer, enabling users to discover research assets while the underlying data remains hosted on external platforms.

Through this interface, users can browse, search, and access metadata that describes datasets, experiments, and other research artifacts produced within the project.

All software components composing the FDMI have been successfully deployed and are operational. The FDMI Catalogue, accessible via a public Web Interface, provides streamlined access to the research products managed within the infrastructure and is available at: <https://greendigit.d4science.org/fdmi>.

2.2 Single Sign-On (SSO) and Federated Identity and Access Management Service (IAM)

The **GreenDIGIT Federated Identity and Access Management (IAM)** system allows users to securely access services using their institutional or other Identity Provider (IdP) (e.g. Google) credentials without the need to register a new account (Figure 3). Standards such as **OpenID Connect (OIDC)** and **SAML** ensure interoperability with federated research institutions.

To obtain an OAuth 2.0 Access Token (Figure 4), GreenDIGIT relies on the SoBigData e-infrastructure, which adopts industry-standard protocols for secure authentication and authorisation. Specifically, it supports OpenID Connect (OIDC) for authentication and User-Managed Access 2.0 (UMA 2) for authorisation. The system issues JSON Web Tokens (JWTs) as Access Tokens, used to securely access services. Figure 3 shows an example of a JWT that can be used to interact with the FDMI APIs.

2.3 FDMI Access via APIs

GreenDIGIT's FDMI access are provided via APIs through the gCat (gCube Catalogue) service, part of SoBigData. This RESTful web service exposes a complete set of operations using standard HTTP methods, supporting full CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) functionality. Access requires a valid JWT Bearer token, ensuring secure and standards-compliant interactions. The service returns appropriate HTTP status codes (e.g. 200 OK, 201 Created, 401 Unauthorized, 404 Not Found, 500 Internal Server Error) in line with REST best practices. Users can integrate gCat into their workflows using any REST client or application.

Documentation is available at: <https://api.d4science.org/gcat/docs/index.html>

Its **source code is released under the European Union Public Licence v.1.2 (EUPL v.1.2)** and is publicly available at: <https://code-repo.d4science.org/gCubeSystem/gcat>

2.4 FDMI Access via Web Interfaces

Figure 5 shows the FDMI Catalogue interface, built on top of CKAN, a widely adopted open-source data management system. The interface allows users to search, access, and manage metadata records for datasets registered within the GreenDIGIT infrastructure. It provides a user-friendly environment for publishing and discovering marine and climate-related resources in alignment with FAIR principles.

Home Organisations Groups Items Types Statistics

GreenDIGIT

As part of the GreenDIGIT initiative, the Federated Data Management Infrastructure (FDMI) provides a scalable, open-source platform for managing, publishing, and discovering research artefacts, such as datasets, methods, and experiment results, across a network of Research Infrastructures. Powered by the SoBigData RI, FDMI enables rich metadata annotation to support reproducible and energy-efficient science, fostering responsible data lifecycle practices in line with the principles of Open Science and GreenDIGIT's sustainability objectives.

All the products are accompanied with rich descriptions capturing general attributes, e.g. title and creator(s), as well as usage policies and licences.

Items Search

See All Items [See All Tags](#)

GreenDIGIT Catalogue statistics

10	1	5	2
items	organisation	groups	types

Browse by Groups

slices ri SLICES-RI (3)	SOBIGDATA SoBigData RI (2)	EBRAINS EBRAINS RI (1)
----------------------------	-------------------------------	---------------------------

[See All Groups](#)

Browse by Types

Experiment (7)	Dataset (3)
----------------	-------------

[See All Types](#)

Popular Formats

[ZIP](#) [application/x-msdos-pro...](#) [HTML](#) [JPEG](#) [PNG](#)

Popular Tags

[Test metadata](#) [sustainability](#) [energyconsumption](#) [reproducibility](#) [energy](#) [measurements](#) [tag](#) [network](#) [DBLP](#) [test](#)

[See All Tags](#)

Figure 5. The FDMI Catalogue interface.

The FDMI Catalogue interface is available at <https://greendigit.d4science.org/fdmi>.

Home Organisations Groups Items Types Statistics My... Publish Item Update Item
Delete Item Share Link Upload to Zenodo

/ Organisations / GreenDIGIT / MoonGen example experiment ...

MoonGen example experiment with energy measurement

Followers
0

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Organisation

GreenDIGIT
GreenDIGIT provides researchers with a web-based platform to design and conduct reproducible experiments while promoting Open Science practices. It streamlines the entire... [read more](#)

License
Academic Free License 3.0 [Open Data](#)

Item Groups Activity Stream

MoonGen example experiment with energy measurement

Example MoonGen experiment executed in SLICES-RI infrastructure. MoonGen generating load packets in different sizes and sending them to a device under test. Consumed energy was measured per node and stored in the energy folder.

Tags
energy measurements reproducibility

Data and Resources
[RO-Crate ZIP Archive](#) [Explore](#)

Item URL
<https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/GreenDIGIT/moongen-example-experiment-with-energy-measurement>

Additional Info

Field	Value
Creation Date	2025-06-13
Creator	Kilian Warmuth
Creator Email	kilian.warmuth@tum.de
Creator Name PI (Principal Investigator)	Kilian Warmuth
Environment OS	Linux
Environment Platform	D4Science GreenDIGIT
Experiment Dependencies	none
Experiment ID	exp-green-digit-001
GreenDIGIT Node	D4Science Pisa
Group	SLICES-RI
Programming Language	Python
Project ID	GD-T5.2
Session reading metrics	enabled
relatedIdentifier:Zenodo.DOI	{ "relatedIdentifierType": "URL", "relationType": "isReferencedBy", "link": "https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18921448", "zenodoId": "18921448" }
system:type	Experiment

Management Info

Field	Value
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Maintainer	Warmuth Kilian
Version	1
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Figure 6. Example of Experiment published in the FDMI.

Figure 6 illustrates the metadata structure and the corresponding payload(s) associated with the example experiment titled “MoonGen example experiment with energy measurement.” It is worth to

note the metadata attribute “relatedidentifier:Zenodo:DOI” valorised with the DOI assigned form Zenodo.

Researchers can programmatically access the FDMI through the dedicated RESTful APIs, which are fully documented and available at: <https://api.d4science.org/catalogue/api-docs/ui/index.html>.

Figure 7. Publishing of a Research product in the FDMI via Web User Interface.

Research Products can be published either via these programmatic interfaces (gCat service) or through user-friendly Web Forms, as shown in Figure 7.

2.5 Publishing on Zenodo

Research Products in the FDMI can be published automatically on Zenodo to ensure FAIR preservation, citation and DOI Minting. The FDMI features a Java component that translates metadata stored in FDMI catalogue records into the format required by Zenodo to create a deposition that can later be edited and published.

The process starts when a user selects an item in the FDMI Catalogue interface. The system retrieves the item and creates a draft Zenodo deposition by translating the core metadata fields (such as title, description, authors, and keywords). If the catalogue item is already linked to an existing Zenodo record, the draft deposition updates the corresponding information to keep the two systems aligned.

The screenshot shows the 'Upload to Zenodo' interface. At the top, there is a warning message: 'By using this process you are transferring selected catalogue item content to the Zenodo Repository (link). This will create a new item in Zenodo and a link of the Zenodo item will be added to the catalogue item.' Below this, the 'Item Information' section is active, showing a form with the following fields:

- Title: ecojupyter_test_green digit_fmri
- Description: EcoJupyter submission for FDMI.
- Keywords: energyconsumption x, metadata x, test x
- Upload type: other
- Access right: open
- License: AFL-3.0

At the bottom right of the form is an 'Upload to Zenodo' button. Below the form, a table displays the metadata for the item:

Field	Value
Creation Date	2025-07-03 12:13
Creator	Gonçalo Ferreira
Creator Email	goncalo.ferreira@student.uva.nl
Creator Name PI (Principal Investigator)	123456789
Environment OS	Mac (macOS 26.0)
Environment Platform	GreenDIGIT
Experiment Dependencies	pandas, plotly
Experiment ID	experiment-6d95b1fd-2025-07-03 12:13
GreenDIGIT Node	node_01

Figure 8. Publishing of a Research product from the FDMI to Zenodo via Web User Interface

Figure 8 shows the FDMI Web UI to publish on Zenodo, to support different types of catalogue items, the Web UI underlying mechanism uses configurable XML mappings. These mappings define how specific metadata fields in the FDMI Catalogue should be transferred to the appropriate fields in Zenodo. The mappings are stored in the system configuration and are applied automatically based on the item profile. After the mapping is applied, a complete Zenodo deposition is generated and returned to the catalogue interface, where users can review or edit the information before final publication.

Once the user confirms publication, the dataset is deposited in Zenodo and a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) is assigned. This DOI is then automatically recorded back in the FDMI Catalogue entry, ensuring a persistent link between the catalogue record and the published dataset.

Overall, the library provides a simple and flexible mechanism for connecting catalogue-based research infrastructures with Zenodo, enabling researchers to publish datasets and obtain persistent identifiers while maintaining consistency between catalogue metadata and repository records. Figure 9 shows an actual FDMI Item in Zenodo, also visible at this link: <https://zenodo.org/records/18921448>

The screenshot shows the Zenodo interface for a record titled "MoonGen example experiment with energy measurement" by Warmuth Kilian. The record is published on March 9, 2026, and is version 1. The main content area displays a file tree for "RO-Crate_ZIP_Archive.zip" with the following structure:

- config
 - 2025-04-25_17-04-08_588085_variables.json (264 Bytes)
 - allocation.json (824 Bytes)
 - valga
 - hardware.json (24.4 kB)
 - topology.json (2.9 kB)
 - topology.pdf (78.5 kB)
- energy
 - valga
 - measurement_run00.csv (2.2 kB)
 - measurement_run01.csv (2.2 kB)
 - measurement_run02.csv (2.2 kB)
 - measurement_run03.csv (2.2 kB)
 - measurement_run04.csv (2.2 kB)
 - measurement_run05.csv (2.2 kB)
 - measurement_run06.csv (2.2 kB)
 - measurement_run07.csv (2.2 kB)
 - measurement_run08.csv (2.2 kB)
 - measurement_run09.csv (2.2 kB)
 - experiment_recording.json (5.5 kB)
- files
- ro-crate-metadata.json (71.3 kB)
- scripts
 - valga

The right sidebar contains several sections: "Actions" (Edit, New version, Share), "Views and Downloads" (5 Views, 0 Downloads), "Versions" (Version 1, 10.5281/zenodo.18921448, Mar 9, 2026), "External resources" (Indexed in OpenAIRE), "Communities" (GreenDIGIT FDMI Staging), "Keywords and subjects" (energy measurements, reproducibility), and "Details" (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18921448, Resource type: Other, Publisher: Zenodo).

Figure 9. The actual deposited Research Product in Zenodo

3 Conclusion

The GreenDIGIT Federated Data Management Infrastructure (FDMI), developed on the SoBigData platform, provides a robust environment for publishing, discovering, and reusing datasets, workflows, and experiment results. Through secure Single Sign-On, standards-based APIs, and a user-friendly web interface, researchers can easily register and share their outputs in line with FAIR and reproducibility principles. A key capability of the infrastructure is the Zenodo Export functionality, which allows catalogue items to be seamlessly published in the Zenodo open repository. Through this mechanism, metadata and resources registered in the FDMI Catalogue can be automatically translated into Zenodo depositions, enabling researchers to obtain a persistent DOI and make their outputs publicly accessible. This export mechanism ensures that catalogue records remain synchronised with the corresponding Zenodo publication, preserving a clear link between the FDMI entry and the archived dataset.

By combining Federated Data Management service with metadata profiles, automated export and publication features, FDMI ensures that research data and results can be disseminated broadly, cited reliably, and preserved for long-term accessibility, strengthening the visibility and reuse of outputs produced within the GreenDIGIT ecosystem.